

IMPACT OF UNCERTAINTIES ON MISTUNED FORCED RESPONSE PREDICTIONS IN A TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR BLISK

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ABSTRACT

Striving towards accurate forced response analysis for blisks is currently challenging, where the need to validate against experimental data is essential to understand the inherent numerical uncertainties. These uncertainties can propagate within the forced response analysis chain, causing significant inaccuracies in the vibrational amplitudes. The blisk of a 1.5 transonic compressor stage at the TU Darmstadt test facility is considered in the investigation. The stage contains a wake generator that can be configured to modify the wakes impinging on the rotor from upstream, while subjected to potential fields from downstream, both are assessed in a transient stage analysis as the main contributors to the pressure fluctuation. This has been performed in two ways, using a temporal transformation on the interfaces with relative motion, and running a full 360° stage analysis. The aerodynamic damping analysis has been performed using a temporal Fourier series at the periodic interfaces and with non-reflecting boundary conditions. The mode of interest has been prescribed on the rotor, where the aerodynamic damping obtained from the work per cycle has been assessed for different operating points. The results show a satisfactory validation of the aerodynamic damping against experiments, however, large inaccuracies are still present when validating the vibrational amplitude. Mistuned forced response analyses are conducted to investigate the distribution of vibrational energy around the blisk and to gain deeper insight into the nature and sources of these uncertainties.

NOMENCLATURE

ACRONYMS

FEM	Finite Element Model
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
COV	Coefficient Of Variance
PE	Peak Efficiency
NC	Near Choke
NS	Near Stall
TT	Time-Transformation
TUDa	Technical University of Darmstadt
VIGV	Variable Inlet Guide Vane
WG	Wake Generator

SYMBOLS

ABS	Absolute	[-]
\Re	Real component	[-]
\Im	Imaginary component	[-]
P	Pressure	[Pa]
\hat{P}	Unsteady pressure	[Pa]
mod	Modification	[-]
Sec	Sector CFD domain	[-]

1 INTRODUCTION

As gas turbine designs evolve to meet the challenge of reducing emissions, thinner and more heavily loaded blades have made these turbines increasingly susceptible to vibrations. To assess the severity of such vibrations and the associated risk of high-cycle fatigue, forced response analyses are commonly performed. However, these analyses are subject to various sources of uncertainty, and reducing their influence has remained a persistent challenge over the years.

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To assess the impact of these uncertainties in forced response predictions, several strategies can be employed. These include using alternative methods to compute aerodynamic excitation, examining the influence of CFD and FEM discretization choices, and incorporating mistuning effects. By applying these approaches at specific resonant crossings, it becomes possible to quantify the associated uncertainties. The resulting numerical predictions can then be compared with experimental data to validate the accuracy and robustness of the analysis.

Mistuning in bladed-disks originates from minor imperfections such as wear, deterioration, damage, corrosion, or manufacturing tolerances. These imperfections are unavoidable in practical applications and disrupt the harmonic patterns of traveling wave modes (TWM). While this paper focuses on its effect on forced response amplitudes, its influence on aerodynamic damping is significantly important. Studies have shown that mistuning can enhance rotor stability, as discussed by Srinivasan [1], and by Kaza and Kielb [2], as well as Yang et al. [3], particularly when alternate mistuning is applied. This stabilizing effect is attributed to mistuning breaking the traveling wave patterns and reducing aerodynamic coupling between blades, thereby limiting the transfer of vibrational energy. In addition to affecting aerodynamic damping, structural mistuning alters blade-to-blade interactions, localizing vibrational energy in certain sectors of the blisk and reducing forced response amplitude in those regions. Ewins [4] was among the first to study mistuning, reporting up to a 20% increase in resonant stress levels depending on the specific blade arrangement. Whitehead [5] later established the maximum amplification limit as $(\frac{1+\sqrt{N}}{2})$. Mistuning can be analyzed probabilistically, as demonstrated by Sinha and Chen [6] using high-order analytical techniques, or it can be introduced intentionally by modifying the structural properties of the bladed-disk as in Gutierrez et al. [7].

Computational constraints in resolving the unsteady pressure field resulting from upstream and downstream excitations on a specific rotor have led to the adoption of various methods for calculating the forcing function. One approach involves scaling the computational domain while maintaining constant solidity and achieving spatial periodicity in the adjacent blade row, as demonstrated by Mayorca et al. [8]. Alternative techniques, such as harmonic balance, utilize multiple harmonics to more accurately capture the flow field, as described by Gross et al. [9] and Schoenenborn [10]. It is important to account for the uncertainties associated with each method to ensure reliable results, with full 360° transient analysis serving as the benchmark for accuracy.

A further limitation in mistuned forced response analysis is the need to retain detailed information for all blades, requiring storage of the full stiffness and mass matrices for each blade. This leads to a system with a high number of degrees of freedom. To manage the associated computational cost, reduced or-

der models (ROMs) are widely used to facilitate efficient analysis. Several ROMs have been proposed for predicting forced response amplitudes, Gutierrez et al. [11] compared three such models, highlighting their versatility and accuracy. For cases with high mistuning, the Craig–Bampton multisubstructuring (M) approach provides high accuracy by spanning the reduced space with mistuned modes and without assuming cyclic symmetry. However, this method is less efficient for low mistuning levels, where a subset of nominal modes with cyclic symmetry is preferable. In practice, mistuning levels are typically low, especially when random or probabilistic mistuning is present in manufactured blisks.

Validating numerical results against experimental data is crucial for assessing accuracy and identifying key factors during forced response simulations at the design stage, as demonstrated by Besem et al. [12]. Similarly, Mayorca et al. [13] showed how various sources of uncertainty affect forced response predictions, particularly highlighting how uncertainty in aerodynamic damping can influence overall vibration amplitude.

The Technical University of Darmstadt (TUDa) rotor blisk has served as a benchmark case for investigating such phenomena. The TUDa test rig has been extensively studied in previous works, including numerical validation of forced response against experiments by Kilian et al. [14], aeroelastic effects of inlet guide vane mistuning (Franke et al. [15]), and self-excited blade vibration (Holzinger et al. [16]), among others. Recognized as an open test case, the rig is well-equipped for comprehensive aerodynamic and aeromechanical investigations, as described by Klausmann et al. [17].

This paper focuses on the numerical aspects of mistuned forced response analysis, specifically investigating how different sources of uncertainty propagate through the analysis chain and influence the resulting amplitude response. As noted by Seinturier [18], "The forced response prediction in the design process gives very useful information to engineers. But it also rises many questions, due to the number of influencing parameters, not always easy to identify.

2 METHODOLOGY

The TUDa test rig is a 1.5-stage high-pressure transonic compressor. The experiments, carried out under the scope of the of the EU-funded ARiAS project, utilized a configuration comprising 8 Variable Inlet Guide Vanes (VIGV) or Wake Generator (WG), a rotor (R) with 16 blades, 29 downstream stator vanes (S) and 5 struts (ST). The rig is equipped with high-fidelity instrumentation capable of capturing both steady and unsteady flow characteristics, as detailed by Klausmann et al. [19]. An overview of the compressor stage is provided in Figure 1.

The pressure fluctuations on the rotor are primarily driven by upstream wake impingement and downstream potential field effects, both of which are evaluated in a stage analysis. Two ap-

proaches are employed: a sector-domain simulation utilizing the time-transformation (TT) method (Giles [20]) across the interfaces, and a full 360° transient simulation. To evaluate aerodynamic damping, a dedicated analysis was conducted using a temporal Fourier series applied at the periodic interfaces, along with non-reflecting boundary conditions. The rotor was prescribed with the mode of interest, and the aerodynamic damping was quantified based on the work-per-cycle method. The structural mesh was generated with ICEM, while the aerodynamic domain was discretized using ANSYS Turbogrid.

The mistuned forced response analysis was then performed using ANSYS Workbench, employing the Component Mode Mistuning (CMM) reduced-order model described in Lim et al. [22], which is a variant of the well-established Component Mode Substructure (CMS) method. This reduction technique is tailored for small mistuning levels, as it retains cyclic symmetry. The limitations of this approach have been demonstrated by Gutierrez et al. [11].

FIGURE 1: TUDa 1.5 stage model. (Reproduced from Klausmann et al. [17].)

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The forced response prediction framework integrates structural and aerodynamic analyses to evaluate mistuned blade behavior. FEM provides the stiffness and mass matrices corresponding to the relevant vibration modes, while CFD simulations supply the unsteady aerodynamic damping and excitation forces. This combined dataset forms the basis for accurately predicting the mistuned forced response, enabling a detailed assessment of the dynamic behavior under realistic operating conditions.

Finite Element Model

A FEM of a sector of the blisk was generated using ANSYS ICEM, employing a structured hexahedral mesh. The full 360° model, reconstructed by expanding the sector model, is illustrated in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: FEM domain of the TUDa rotor.

Figure 3 presents the frequencies of the first three mode families, derived from a static analysis followed by a modal analysis. The 80% nominal speed (N_c) line, corresponding to 16,000 rpm, is also included. A resonance crossing is clearly identified in Mode 2 at eight nodal diameters (8ND), corresponding to the first torsional mode due to upstream wakes from the VIGV. This particular crossing was selected for investigating uncertainties in the forced response predictions and for validating the numerical results against experimental data.

Computational Fluid Dynamics

Steady-state CFD results were obtained for various operating points and then compared with the experimental speed lines, as shown in Figure 4. Two speed lines are presented: one for the baseline case with the variable inlet guide vanes (VIGV) set at 0° (Pattern F) and another with the vanes rotated to 15° (Pattern FP15). Three operating points are marked for each speed line, representing near choke (NC), peak efficiency (PE) and near stall (NS) conditions. The continuous line represents the CFD results using boundary conditions consistent with the experimental setup. However, to achieve better alignment with the experimental speed lines, the inlet total temperature was slightly adjusted. Although this modification was necessary, it introduces an uncertainty that, if not properly accounted for, may propagate into subsequent analyses.

The computational domain employed for the steady-state

FIGURE 3: Frequency of three mode families versus ND including part-speed crossing.

FIGURE 4: TUDa stage compressor map.

ANSYS CFX simulations is shown in Figure 5a with only one sector per blade row. A mesh independence study was conducted to ensure solution accuracy, resulting in the selection of a grid comprising approximately 4.2 million nodes. This mesh was used to compute the steady pressure distribution on the rotor, which served as input for the FEM static analysis and for the initiation of the unsteady aerodynamic and damping simulations.

Aerodynamic Damping To evaluate the aerodynamic damping, the energy method outlined by Carta [21] was employed. This approach involves normalizing the aerodynamic work by the kinetic energy of the system. The unsteady simulations were conducted in ANSYS using the Fourier transformation method on only the rotor domain as shown in Figure 5c. The resulting damping ratios across various operating conditions are illustrated in Figure 6 for Pattern F case, and Figure 7 for Pattern FP15 case.

The aerodynamic damping values computed for the modi-

FIGURE 5: CFD domains.

FIGURE 6: Aerodynamic damping for Pattern F, Mode 2.

fied operating points exhibit close agreement with those obtained under unmodified boundary conditions, with a maximum relative deviation of 7%, observed for Pattern F NC. This indicates that the use of approximate operating conditions for the aerodynamic damping introduces negligible uncertainty and does not significantly compromise the accuracy of the forced response predictions. Furthermore, the aerodynamic damping values across all six operating points for Patterns F and FP15 fall within the bounds of the experimental data. Although the damping trends along the corrected mass flow show deviations from those observed experimentally, the discrepancies are not expected to substantially influence the forced response analysis. Overall, the uncertainties associated with the comparison between simulated and experimental aerodynamic damping are considered to have a minimal impact on the reliability of the predictions.

Aerodynamic Forcing Aerodynamic forcing calculations were performed exclusively for the modified cases corresponding to Pattern F and FP15, encompassing six operating points as illustrated in Figure 4. To quantify the unsteady pressure distributions on the rotor, the influence of impinging wakes

FIGURE 7: Aerodynamic damping for Pattern FP15, Mode 2.

from the eight Variable Inlet Guide Vanes (VIGVs) and the potential fields generated by the 29 downstream stator blades were analyzed. These effects, visualized in Figure 8, represent critical inputs for the forced response analysis of the rotor.

FIGURE 8: Left: Visualization of wake structures using turbulence eddy frequency contours for Pattern FP15 mod. (360 1T-1T). Right: Potential field effects represented by static pressure contours for Pattern F mod. (360 1T-1T).

The aerodynamic forcing was evaluated using two computational domains: a sector model, as shown in Figure 5b, and a full 360° model, depicted in Figure 5d. Interface boundary conditions between blade rows were defined using transient interfaces for the full annular domain and TT methods for the sector model. To reduce computational cost, a mixing-plane approach was also considered as an alternative. However, this simplification disrupts the transmission of flow perturbations from the stator to the rotor, thus preventing the interaction of pressure waves across blade rows. To assess the uncertainties associated with this sim-

plification, both domain configurations were additionally tested with mixing-plane interfaces between the rotor and stator, as detailed in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Overview of the computational configurations adopted for the aerodynamic forcing simulations.

Cases	VIGV-Rotor	Rotor-Stator
360 1T-1M	Transient	Mixing-Plane
360 1T-1T	Transient	Transient
Sec 1TT-1M	Time-Transformation	Mixing-Plane
Sec 1TT-1TT	Time-Transformation	Time-Transformation

The results show high unsteady pressure levels in regions where the Mach number is also high, as shown in Figure 9. This trend intensifies along the span, suggesting that the interaction between the wake and the shock wave is a primary driver of the observed unsteadiness. The effect is particularly pronounced near the blade tip, where the local tangential velocity is the highest.

FIGURE 9: Mach number visualization for Pattern FP15 mod (360 1T-1T) at three spanwise locations, overlaid with blade unsteady pressure fields. Mach number contours range from 0 to 1.1. (Units: [-].) Unsteady pressure contours are not shown.

Figure 10 presents the real component of the unsteady pressure for Pattern F mod, while Figure 11 shows the corresponding imaginary component. The data have been separated into real

and imaginary parts to avoid combining them into a single absolute magnitude, which would distort the differences and make direct comparison more difficult. It can be observed qualitatively that the pressure distribution associated to the shock wave is consistent across all cases. However, differences emerge when comparing the two domain configurations. Notably, the cases with mixing-plane interfaces, for both in the full 360° and sector models, exhibit greater similarity to each other than to their respective counterparts without mixing planes. For instance, the 360 1T-1M configuration shows closer agreement in both real and imaginary pressure distributions with the Sec 1T-1M case than with the 360 1T-1T case, despite sharing the same full annular domain. However, this trend is not observed for Pattern FP15 mod, as illustrated in Figure 14 and Figure 15, where the pressure distributions appear to vary more significantly with the domain configuration than with the interface condition.

Another parameter considered for comparison is the generalized force. This quantity is obtained by projecting the unsteady aerodynamic forces onto the structural mode shape, which in this case is the torsional mode depicted in Figure 3. This approach provides deeper insight into how unsteady pressure distributions contribute to work input on the blade, thus influencing vibrational amplitudes. It is important to note that not all pressure acting on the blade contributes equally to the vibrational response, since the effect depends on the spatial alignment of the pressure distribution relative to the mode shape displacements. This provides a more accurate representation of how unsteady pressure contributes to work input and influences vibrational amplitudes.

As shown in Figure 12, the generalized force is significantly more pronounced on the suction side, which directly faces the VIGV and its wakes, compared to the pressure side facing the stators. Interestingly, the similarities observed in the unsteady pressure distributions between cases with mixing-plane interfaces, both in the full 360° and sector models, do not translate to the generalized force magnitude. In fact, the full 360° configurations exhibit higher force magnitudes than their sector model counterparts.

However, when examining the generalized force phase in Figure 13, the similarities between mixing-plane cases remain evident. The spatial distribution of the phase, particularly the localized blue and red regions, shows qualitative agreement between the 360 1T-1M and Sec 1T-1M configurations, especially on the pressure side facing the stator and near the tip region of the suction side.

Similar trends are observed for Pattern FP15 mod in Figure 16, where the full 360° configurations again exhibit higher generalized force magnitudes. However, in this case, the regions of maximum force are located closer to the blade leading edge. Notably, high force magnitudes are observed on the pressure side for both 360 1T-1M and 360 1T-1T. A key difference between Pattern F mod (Figure 12) and Pattern FP15 mod (Figure 16) is the spatial distribution of the generalized force relative to the tor-

sional mode shape. In Pattern F mod, the force is concentrated in two distinct regions separated by a node line near mid-chord (marked by a dashed black line in Figure 12e), where the force drops to zero. In contrast, Pattern FP15 mod exhibits a more localized concentration of maximum force near the leading edge.

FIGURE 10: Real component of the unsteady pressure distribution for Pattern F mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Pressure contours range from -2000 to 2000. (Units: [Pa].)

FIGURE 11: Imaginary component of the unsteady pressure distribution for Pattern F mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Pressure contours range from -2000 to 2000. (Units: [Pa].)

FIGURE 12: Generalized force magnitude distribution for Pattern F mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Magnitude contours range from 0 to 0.0020. (Units: [N].)

FIGURE 13: Generalized force phase distribution for Pattern F mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Phase contours range from -180 to 180. (Units: [°].)

Forced Response

A tuned forced response analysis was carried out for the three operating points (NC, PE, and NS) of Pattern F mod and Pattern FP15 mod using the forcing function from the Sec 1TT-1TT configuration. The aerodynamic damping values applied in each case are those presented in Figure 6 for Pattern F mod and in Figure 7 for Pattern FP15 mod. The resulting tuned vibrational amplitude responses are shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19, respectively. For all six operating points across the two patterns, the predicted tuned maximum amplitudes are significantly underestimated compared to the experimental data, with the largest discrepancies observed under NC conditions.

Mistuning is introduced as a parameter that modifies the Young's modulus of each blade relative to its nominal value.

FIGURE 14: Real component of the unsteady pressure distribution for Pattern FP15 mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Pressure contours range from -2000 to 2000. (Units: [Pa].)

FIGURE 15: Imaginary component of the unsteady pressure distribution for Pattern FP15 mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Pressure contours range from -2000 to 2000. (Units: [Pa].)

Since the natural frequency is proportional to the Young's modulus, this modification results in a corresponding frequency shift in every blade. The analysis was performed for a single operating point (PE) of both Pattern F mod and Pattern FP15 mod, using the forcing functions derived from all available configurations. For the mistuned blisk, frequency deviations obtained from experimental ping tests were used as input to the FEM to compute the mistuned response. According to Whitehead [5], the theoretical maximum amplification factor due to mistuning is 2.5, calculated as $\frac{1+\sqrt{16}}{2} = 2.5$. In the present analysis, the amplification factors resulting from the mistuning using the forcing function from the Sec 1TT-1TT configuration were 1.338 for Pattern F mod and

FIGURE 16: Generalized force magnitude distribution for Pattern FP15 mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Magnitude contours range from 0 to 0.0020. (Units: [N].)

FIGURE 17: Generalized force phase distribution for Pattern FP15 mod. (Top: Pressure side. Bottom: Suction side.) Phase contours range from -180 to 180. (Units: [°].)

1.375 for Pattern FP15 mod. Despite accounting for mistuning, the predicted maximum amplitudes remain underestimated when compared to the experimental data.

Propagation of Uncertainties

To develop a comprehensive understanding of the uncertainties that propagate to the final results, specifically the mistuned forced response amplitude, several parameters were examined to evaluate their influence and to identify the most significant contributors. These parameters include the number of nodes used in the discretization of the FEM, the forcing functions derived from different domain configurations, and the variability introduced when modeling mistuning.

FIGURE 18: Maximum amplitude at the leading edge tip for Mode 2 of Pattern F mod. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

FIGURE 19: Maximum amplitude at the leading edge tip for Mode 2 of Pattern FP15 mod. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

Finite Element Model Mesh A detailed comparison between different FEM discretizations was achieved. The objective was twofold: first, to quantify the impact of the total number of nodes on the blade, since the disk region had the same number of nodes in all cases ($\approx 47,000$ nodes), on the natural frequency as well as on the tuned and mistuned maximum amplitudes; and second, to evaluate the importance of using quadratic instead of linear element types in the FEM analysis. As shown in Figure 20, convergence is achieved in both cases as the number of nodes increases. However, it is important to note that the quadratic mesh consistently reaches convergence with fewer nodes compared to the linear one. For example, the 150/40-Linear is less accurate than 50/28-Quadratic, even though both contain approximately 70,000 nodes on the blade. In other words, for the same computational cost, the quadratic mesh provides more accurate results. It is also important to highlight that the discretization affects not

TABLE 2: Maximum vibrational amplitudes and amplification factors for Pattern F mod at the leading edge tip obtained using the forcing functions from the different domain configurations. (Units: [μm]. FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

Cases	Tuned	Mistuned	Amp. Factor
360 1T-1M	94.8	127.1	1.341
360 1T-1T	61.1	81.7	1.337
Sec 1TT-1M	81.2	109	1.342
Sec 1TT-1TT	49.7	66.5	1.338

TABLE 3: Maximum vibrational amplitudes and amplification factors for Pattern FP15 mod at the leading edge tip obtained using the forcing functions from the different domain configurations. (Units: [μm]. FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

Cases	Tuned	Mistuned	Amp. Factor
360 1T-1M	17.8	23.3	1.309
360 1T-1T	15.4	21.3	1.383
Sec 1TT-1M	16.2	21.0	1.296
Sec 1TT-1TT	24.8	34.1	1.375

only the structural response but also the accuracy of the pressure on the blade is more accurately mapped with a denser mesh.

Figure 21 presents a comparison of the frequencies obtained from the mistuned forced response analysis for all FEM discretizations across each blade. In this analysis, the Young’s modulus was adjusted to match the frequency deviations observed in the experimental ping tests. Two main observations can be made. First, applying the frequency deviations from the ping test does not fully reproduce the frequency deviations measured by blade tip timing in the experiments. The shaded region in the figure represents the maximum and minimum values from the blade tip timing data, with the dashed line indicating the mean. While the overall trend along the blade is reasonably captured, some predicted frequencies fall outside this range. Second, despite the differences in mesh density, the frequency deviations are very similar across all meshes. This indicates that the uncertainty introduced by the mapping of unsteady pressure, as well as the differences in natural frequency is negligible in the mistuned forced response analysis when using a coarser mesh. Therefore,

FIGURE 20: Natural frequency as a function of the total number of nodes on the blade. The number of spanwise elements (above) and chordwise elements (below) is indicated for each case. (Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

FIGURE 21: Comparison of frequency deviations from different FEM mesh discretizations, based on ping test inputs in the simulation compared to the experimental blade tip timing measurements. (Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

the 40/22-Linear mesh case, despite exhibiting a relative difference in natural frequency of approximately 0.25% compared to the converged cases shown in Figure 20, is suitable for accurately predicting frequency deviation in a mistuned forced response analysis.

A similar conclusion can be drawn from the maximum amplitude observed in the tuned forced response analysis. As shown in Figure 22, the relative differences in maximum unsteady displacement are considered negligible across all discretizations, remaining below 2%.

Lastly, a comparison of the maximum amplitudes profiles

FIGURE 22: Maximum unsteady displacement at the leading edge tip as a function of the total number of nodes on the blade. The number of spanwise elements (above) and chordwise elements (below) is indicated for each case. (Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

obtained from the mistuned forced response analysis is presented in Figure 23. The left axis indicates the maximum tip displacements from the simulations, and on the right axis, are the experimental maximum tip displacements. It has been plotted this way, since the simulations amplitudes are almost one order of magnitude less than the experiments, which allows an easier comparison. It is also qualitatively evident that the mistuned response shows minimal variation across the different mesh discretizations, where the maximum relative difference in amplitude occurring for 300/150-Linear and 100/40-Linear is of approximately 2%.

The mistuned response shows minimal sensitivity to mesh discretization, with the largest relative difference in amplitude, also approximately 2%, occurring between the 300/150-Linear and 100/40-Linear meshes.

Aerodynamic Forcing The influence of configuration differences in the aerodynamic forcing has been investigated for the Pattern F mod case, as detailed in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 24. The maximum amplitude for the 360 1T-1M configuration is 92% greater than that of the single sector with periodicity (Sec 1TT-1TT). Configurations incorporating a mixing plane, such as Sec 1TT-1M and 360 1T-1M, consistently yield higher amplitudes than their counterparts without a mixing plane. For the Pattern FP15 mod case, all configurations produce similar results, except for Sec 1TT-1TT, which exhibits a maximum amplitude approximately 61% greater than that of the other configurations, as shown in Table 3. The amplification factors for both patterns are comparable across all configurations, particularly when comparing with mixing plane cases (Sec 1TT-1M and 360 1T-1M) and without them (Sec 1TT-1TT and 360 1T-1T). For both patterns, the frequency deviations among the different

FIGURE 23: Forced response sweep for different FEM discretizations. Ping test frequency deviations are used as simulation input and compared with experimental blade tip timing data. Left axis: Simulation results. Right axis: Experimental measurements. (Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

FIGURE 24: Forced response sweep using forcing functions from different domain configurations. Ping test frequency deviations are used as simulation input and compared with experimental blade tip timing data. Left axis: Simulation results. Right axis: Experimental measurements. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

forcing functions are negligible, as shown in Figure 25 for the staggered configuration (Pattern FP15 mod).

Mistuning Mistuning effects in blisks are influenced by several factors, including the spatial distribution of mistuning across blades and the overall mistuning level. The nature of the vibration mode, whether blade dominated or disk dominated, plays a critical role in how energy localizes within the structure. In blade dominated modes, as observed at the studied resonance point, the energy tends to be more uniformly distributed across

FIGURE 25: Comparison of frequency deviations of forcing functions from different domain configurations of Pattern FP15 mod, based on ping test inputs in the simulation compared to the experimental blade tip timing measurements. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic.)

FIGURE 26: Comparison of frequency deviations from different mistuning levels of Pattern F mod, based on ping test inputs in the simulation compared to the experimental blade tip timing measurements. (FEM mesh: 150/76-Quadratic. Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

blades, and the system can be approximated as a set of weakly coupled single degree of freedom systems. In contrast, disk dominated modes exhibit stronger energy localization due to the ability of the disk to transfer vibrational energy between sectors, resulting in concentrated response regions.

In the experimental setup, the mistuning pattern derived from ping test frequency deviations is not perfectly captured in the blade tip timing measurements. This suggests a weak coupling between the blades and the disk, which influences the observed response. In contrast, the simulation assumes idealized conditions with negligible disk blade coupling, allowing clearer interpretation of mistuning effects.

To investigate the propagation of mistuning uncertainty, two mistuning patterns were considered: one derived directly from the ping test measurements and another inferred from blade tip timing data. A parametric study was conducted using different values of the coefficient of variation (COV), such as 0.9, 1.0, and 1.1. The coefficient was applied to the frequency deviations obtained from experimental data, representing the normalized variability across blades. These deviations were then converted into stiffness variations by squaring the scaled values, reflecting the quadratic relationship between frequency and stiffness. A coefficient of 1.0 corresponds to the baseline case, preserving the original mistuning distribution. Slightly lower and higher values, like 0.9 and 1.1 respectively, were used to simulate reduced and amplified uncertainty levels, accounting for potential manufacturing tolerances or modeling variability.

The effect of modifying mistuning levels is illustrated in Figure 26, which shows the frequency deviations for COV values ranging from 0.8% to 1.1%, based on the mistuning pattern derived from ping test measurements. It is evident that the ex-

perimental trend cannot be reproduced by simply decreasing or increasing the COV. However, when the frequency deviations obtained from blade tip timing measurements are used instead, the simulation results shown in Figure 28 demonstrate that the experimental data can be matched. Multiple COV values were tested to identify the best fit, which occurs at $COV = 1.1\%$.

The maximum amplitude at the leading edge for the two mistuning patterns is presented in Figure 27 and Figure 29, corresponding to the ping test and blade tip timing frequencies, respectively. While the overall amplitude levels are similar, the blade tip timing pattern exhibits a frequency split with two peaks of nearly equal magnitude, consistent with the experimental data (Exp Mean). This characteristic is not observed in the ping test pattern. Furthermore, increasing the COV leads to a more pronounced frequency split, with the second peak shifting further away in both mistuning patterns. As previously noted, $COV = 1.0\%$ yields a response profile similar to the experimental data for the ping test pattern, while $COV = 1.1\%$ provides the best match for the blade tip timing pattern, as clearly shown in the figures. Despite these adjustments, the amplitude differences between the simulations and experimental measurements remain significant in all cases.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A mistuned forced response analysis was conducted on the TUDa transonic compressor blisk rotor and validated against experimental measurements. Key sources of uncertainty, independent from the experimental data, were systematically investigated:

FIGURE 27: Forced response sweep from different mistuning levels of Pattern F mod. Ping test frequency deviations are used as simulation input and compared with experimental blade tip timing data. Left axis: Simulation results. Right axis: Experimental measurements. (FEM mesh: 150/76-Quadratic. Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

FIGURE 29: Forced response sweep from different mistuning levels of Pattern F mod. Blade tip timing frequency deviations are used as simulation input and compared with experimental blade tip timing data. Left axis: Simulation results. Right axis: Experimental measurements. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic. Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

FIGURE 28: Comparison of frequency deviations from different mistuning levels of Pattern F mod, based on blade tip timing inputs in the simulation compared to the experimental blade tip timing measurements. (FEM mesh: 50/28-Quadratic. Domain configuration: 360 1T-1T.)

and amplitude for both the tuned ($\approx 2\%$) and mistuned ($\approx 2\%$) cases. The maximum relative difference in amplitude occurs between the 300/150-Linear and 100/40-Linear meshes. These results suggest that a coarser mesh can be used without compromising the accuracy of the predictions.

- The influence of domain configuration on the computed aerodynamic forcing was investigated to assess its impact on the forced response predictions. The maximum amplitude difference occurs for Pattern F mod using the full 360° model with mixing-plane (360 1T-1M) configuration, which is 92% greater than that of the single sector periodic case (Sec 1TT-1TT). Frequency differences across configurations are negligible. The domain configuration was identified as the primary contributor to uncertainty propagation in the forced response predictions.

- Two mistuning patterns were considered: one based on ping test measurements and another derived from blade tip timing data. The best-fit coefficient of variation values for these patterns are 1.0% and 1.1%, respectively, with a corresponding relative difference in predicted amplitude between them of approximately 11%.

- The aerodynamic damping values computed for the modified operating points exhibit close agreement with those obtained under unmodified boundary conditions, with a maximum relative deviation of 7%. Uncertainties arising solely from the comparison between simulated and experimental aerodynamic damping are considered to have a minimal impact on the accuracy of the forced response predictions.

- Finite element model mesh resolution has a negligible effect on the response in terms of frequency ($\approx 0.25\%$)

All investigated sources of uncertainty showed limited impact on the forced response prediction, with the exception of the domain configuration used in the aerodynamic forcing computation. However, other sources of uncertainty and underlying physical phenomena not considered in this study may contribute to the underestimation of the experimental amplitudes and should be addressed in future work.

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